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H1 ISC (ISC)	Link
hang.yu@LIGO.ORG - posted 20:40, Thursday 27 December 2018 - last comment - 18:00, Tuesday 15 January 2019(46178)	
ASC error point calibrated in rad/rHz	
Dan, Hang	
Using the dithering lines we set up for the past few days for sensing matrix measurement, and the suspension calibration provided in DCC:T1100378, we calibrated the spectra of the ASC error points into physical rad/rHz. The results were attached.	
The best sensor we have is AS45 for DHARD, and the sensing noise is $\sim 1e-14$ rad/rHz. While a single QPD has a sensing noise similar to AS45, when we use a QPD combo for CHARD to decouple CSOFT, the sensing noise get slightly worse at $\sim 3e-14$ rad/rHz level. The soft loops' sensing noise is about a factor of 10 higher than the hard loops at a few $\times 1e-13$ rad/rHz level.	
On the other hand, the REFL sensors are significantly noisier than AS45/TR QPDs. Using the REFL sensors the CHARD sensitivity is only $1e-12$ rad/rHz at 10 Hz and the slope suggests that it is not shot noise limited. This indicates the necessity of doing CHARD blend from the noise point of view.	
Non-image files attached to this report	
yaw_err_pt.pdf	
Comments related to this report	
hang.yu@LIGO.ORG - 18:00, Tuesday 15 January 2019 (46453)	Link
For future reference, the calibrations are (from L3 physical angle times the output matrix, to the error point of each dof after the input matrix).	
DHARD PIT: $6.8e+10$ [ct/rad]	
DSOFT PIT: $1.0e+5$ [ct/rad]	
CHARD YAW (DC, REFL combo): $2.0e+10$ [ct/rad]	
CHARD YAW (AC, TRQPD combo): $4.3e+10$ [ct/rad]	
CSOFT YAW: $2.1e+5$ [ct/rad]	

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